

CoARA Action Plan UNamur 2025-2030

About

The University of Namur, through the Rectors' Council (CRef), has signed ***The European Charter & Code for Researchers*** which has enabled us to analyse our human resources practices and implement actions to harmonise them using a series of tools:

- Jobs & Funding
- Career Development
- Information & Assistance
- Partnering
- Worldwide

In 2013 UNamur joined Euraxess and received the [***HR Excellence in Research***](#) label from the European Commission, which recognises the quality of the various action plans put in place to improve recruitment, working conditions, careers, and services for researchers.

Through the *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers* label (HRS4R - Euraxess), UNamur is committed to promoting a favourable environment for research, training, and career development.

At UNamur, the action plan is divided into different axes in order to always better implement the principles of the Researcher's Charter such as : networking activities for research, trainings for researchers at all stages of their career, actions to improve the recruitment processes, actions to improve the support offered to PhD students, international researchers, actions on improving working conditions and finally, actions regarding the organisation of activities and entertainment for the research community.

In 2020, our institution joined the European university alliance **UNIVERSEH** – *European Space University for Earth and Humanity* – as part of the European Universities initiative promoted and funded by the European Commission. This alliance of seven universities enables UNamur to develop joint interdisciplinary and intersectoral training courses and programmes, develop innovative teaching models, strengthen mobility and multilingualism in Europe, promote diversity and improve inclusiveness within the alliance and beyond, in the field of space.

Finally, in September 2023, UNamur has signed the [***Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment***](#), thereby becoming a full member of the [***Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment***](#) (CoARA), alongside more than 700 other institutions worldwide. Through this action plan, our institution undertakes to respect and fulfil the commitments of the agreement to the best of its ability.

Priorities and vision shared with CoARA

Strategic plan for research at UNamur

- Promoting Open Access
- Multiple exploitation of research (business, start-up, popularisation of science)
- Definition of the rights and duties of supervisors and doctoral students via a doctoral charter
- Training for PhD students and supervisors

Human Resources Plan:

- Promoting diversity, gender equality and inclusion: UNamur continues its commitment and combines action, analyses, and surveys to emphasise openness, balance and equity.

UNamur has been fully committed to promoting equality. The procedure for hiring new academics must therefore ensure compliance with the principles of gender equality and non-discrimination policy of the University of Namur (session no. 623 of 26 October 2012, Board of Directors, Annex III). The **Isala Nova** project also demonstrates the University of Namur's commitment to this issue. Led by UNamur and UMons, this project relies on collective collaboration to rethink scientific and academic careers from a gender equality perspective.

- Promoting the diversity of contributions and careers in research:

By establishing a **catalogue of cross-disciplinary training courses** for internal researchers and implementing a similar initiative at the inter-university level as part of the FWB/CoARA project (*supra*), UNamur is fulfilling CoARA's first commitment to recognising the diversity of contributions and careers in research. This initiative is also in line with the European Commission's introduction of the **ResearchComp tool** and the **European Charter & Code for Researchers**, which encourages the development of researchers' skills in order to make Europe a land of innovation and scientific excellence. The development of academics' skills, particularly in management, is also promoted through the implementation of a **promoter's career path**, supported by a **supervisor kit**.

Since the beginning of 2024, UNamur has participated in an 18-month inter-university project funded by the Wallonia-Brussels Federation (FWB). The main objective of this project was to develop an inter-university platform for good practices in research evaluation. In line with [CoARA](#)'s commitments, the project was divided into five work packages (WPs), each led by one of the institutions:

Work package	University leader
WP1: Defining new modalities for research assessment	UCLouvain
WP2: Open Science	ULiège
WP3: Ethics	ULB
WP4: Scientific integrity	UMONS
WP5: Training and career development	UNamur

The University of Namur coordinates WP5, which aims to strengthen career support for researchers and talent development. This project will be referred to as "*FWB/CoARA*" for the remainder of the document.

The implementation of the CoARA action plan is now a priority for the University. It fulfils our commitments as a signatory and is in line with the FWB-CoARA project. The implementation of the CoARA action plan has already begun. Actions classified as "high priority" in the plan below are being implemented gradually, in consultation with researchers and with the specific characteristics and international requirements of each field taken into account. Implementation comprises five components:

- Introduce evaluation criteria for Research Council funding, which will consider new types or formats of scientific contribution while maintaining the requirement for scientific rigour. For example, this will enable the recognition of inter- and transdisciplinary project preparation and valorisation initiatives. To do this, we will start by conducting a test with one funding. Then we will extend it to the others if it works.

- Start by evolving the evaluation of projects submitted to the Research Council.
- Next, evolve the evaluation of researchers' CVs at the time of recruitment and promotion applications, in close collaboration with the Vice-Rector for Staff Policy.
- Work on this development with our Belgian (FWB and Flemish) and European partners who are signatories to the agreement, to effect a cultural change in the medium and long term.
- Consolidate the outcomes of the FWB/CoARA project by contributing to the PINDARE inter-university platform hosted on the CRef website (<https://pindare.cref.be/fr/>) and by allocating resources to implement the action plan.

This strategic research plan comprises a number of actions that are aligned with the objectives and commitments set out in the CoARA agreement. These include:

- Axis 2: supporting inter- and transdisciplinary research
- Axis 3: aiming to realise the potential for societal impact and valorisation
- Axis 5: developing Open Science practices

Action plan

By signing the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment on september 2023 and registering as a member of the CoARA coalition, UNamur has committed to publishing an action plan detailing all the measures to be implemented in order to fulfil the 10 commitments of the agreement.

Although research cannot be isolated from the other two institutional missions of teaching and service (to society and to the institution), this document is primarily intended for all those involved in research evaluation within our institution:

- The Research Council, whose role is primarily to evaluate research proposals originating from various calls (e.g., Concerted Research Actions (ARC), Special Research Funds (FSR), etc.)
- Recruitment committees, which perform all evaluations related to the recruitment of new members (e.g., academic positions, qualified researcher positions, etc.)
- Promotion boards, whose role is to evaluate research career progression (e.g., confirmation of position at the end of probationary period or promotion to a higher grade)
- The faculty councils involved in the reappointment of research assistants every two years

This document proposes actions that will not generate excessive administrative complexity or the need to deploy resources that are not currently available. The emphasis is on steps that are already underway and will continue to evolve, feeding into the ongoing reform of research evaluation at UNamur. However, new aspects and initiatives that will be implemented will also be detailed.

Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and the nature of the research.

UNamur already:

- Is committed to supporting inter- and transdisciplinary research through several initiatives that address multiple needs, such as freeing up time to prepare inter- and transdisciplinary projects, recognising inter- and transdisciplinary research in researchers' CV evaluations and training researchers in interdisciplinary research.
- Use a career management tool for each academic to clarify, for the academic and for promotion committees, the expectations of the academic's affiliated entity or entities and/or the University as a whole in terms of expected investment in the three university missions (teaching, research, service to society).
- Considers a wide range of contributions when evaluating research careers.
 - o Three main aspects are assessed when recruiting a new academic member or evaluating their career: the research profile is examined in line with the teaching profile and services provided to society and to the institution. Furthermore, within the evaluated 'Research' section, the section on the researcher's publications is just one aspect of the assessment, as the grid also considers supervisory responsibilities (supervision, doctoral students supervised); scientific recognition (awards, reputation); as well as knowledge transfer, research promotion and research fundings.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Establish a list of criteria for evaluating projects managed by the Research Council, in order to better recognise the diversity of contributions and harmonise the procedure between different calls.
- List instances (outside the Research Council) in which a narrative CV¹ could be required. In these instances, ensure that the use of the narrative CV is benchmarked, and its relevance discussed, to avoid any misuse or excess (e.g., avoid drifts linked to the description of personal rather than professional life). In every other research assessment object or body, ensure that narrative is included and considered.
- Ensure that all evaluation commissions systematically define the list of criteria prior to assessments and share them publicly (as accurately as possible).
- Raise awareness among the actors involved in research assessment of the importance of valuing the involvement of researchers. For example:
 - o In the third mission: services to society and to institution.
 - o In Open Science approaches (such as Open Access publications, FAIR data, etc.).

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

UNamur already:

- Evaluates the research proposals granted via its internal funds (i.e. funds managed by the Research Council) using a peer-review approach that relies primarily on qualitative evaluation.
- Even if there are no explicitly defined criteria, quantitative indicators are rarely used, and when this is the case, such criteria are contextualised and always support qualitative criteria. The Research Council's first criterion for evaluation is an overall appreciation of the project after a comprehensive reading.
- Calls on external experts when needed to consolidate the quality of peer-reviewing (e.g., when assessing large-scale research projects or when recruiting for a new academic position).
- Considers the opinion of the peer reviewers to improve its assessment practices. As part of the FWB/CoARA project, 34 interviews were carried out with members of evaluation committees (including commissions or juries that evaluate research proposals, promotion committees and recruitment committees) to survey their assessment needs and constraints, and to identify potential improvements in the responsible use of quantitative indicators.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Responsible use of quantitative indicators, based on the results of the FWB/CoARA project, together with the partner universities from the FWB.
- **High priority** – In the evaluation of academics, place greater emphasis on the qualitative aspect of papers and their peer-reviewed nature, rather than focusing on the pace of publication and, where applicable, on the 'exceptional bibliometric index' (Grid for supporting and evaluating academic careers, Appendix XIV, 25/11/2020).

¹ A narrative CV is a written account in which researchers can highlight their professional experience, skills and achievements. This narrative format provides a clearer picture of the range of a person's contributions by presenting them in context.

- Increase awareness of the bias of quantitative metrics and the advantages of going to a more qualitative evaluation approach (e.g., by creating a recommendation guide to raise awareness of metric drifts, or by disseminating existing documents on this topic within the institution, particularly among the actors involved in research evaluation).

Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.

UNamur already:

- Does not use the JIF to assess the quality of a candidate's publications as part of the Research Council's research proposal evaluation process.
- Uses the H-index responsibly. Metric indicators are moderated, taking into account the context of the relevant discipline.
- For research projects, candidates are asked to provide abstracts of the five most relevant publications, justifying their choice.
- The majority of project calls ask for a narrative CV to complement the factual CV.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Implement improvements for a responsible use of quantitative indicators, based on the results of the FWB/CoARA project, together with the partner universities from the FWB.
- Increase awareness of the bias of quantitative metrics and the advantages of going to a more qualitative evaluation approach (e.g., by creating a recommendation guide to raise awareness of metric drifts, or by disseminating existing documents on this topic within the institution, particularly among the actors involved in research evaluation).

Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.

UNamur already does not use the ranking of research organisations for research assessment purposes.

Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.

UNamur already:

- Committed resources by hiring a full-time employee to work on the FWB/CoARA project for 18 months. The project aimed to develop an inter-university platform of good practices for research evaluation in line with CoARA. This position will be maintained in order to continue implementing institutional reform beyond the end of the project.
- Mobilised resources as part of the HSR4R Euraxess label through the creation of an internal action plan 2024-2027 defined at UNamur (in particular through actions "Create a recruitment platform" and "Communicate and provide trainings on recruitment procedures").
- Mobilised resources to rethinking the promotion of research in its various aspects (business links, popularisation, Open Access, etc.)
- Dedicating time of the members of the Research Council to steer the process of reforming research assessment within institutional processes.

- Dedicates the time of the members of all recruitment commissions (a unique commission of a minimum of three members is created for each open position) and promotion commissions (a minimum of three members) to all evaluations linked to the career assessment of researchers.

UNamur will:

- Continue to contribute in-kind to the CoARA agreement by:
 - o Dedicating the time of the members of the Research Council to:
 - Steer the process of reforming research assessment within institutional processes.
 - Contribute to the reflection on the use of more qualitative indicators in research evaluation processes, in collaboration with the stakeholders (bottom-up approach).
 - o Dedicating time to the administrative coordination and operationalisation of the implementation of the reform, through the members of the Research Department (ADRE).
 - o However, UNamur will ensure that the processes of the action plan do not overburden the involved resources.

Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.

UNamur already:

- Participate to the working group focusing on defining new indicators for research evaluation as part of the FWB/CoARA project, with the aim of moving towards a more qualitative evaluation of research.
- Produced, as part of the FWB/CoARA project, an institutional inventory of practices (criteria used, procedures and composition of committees) for the assessment of research projects led by the Research Council, and in the assessment of research careers (promotion and recruitment committees).
- Participated, as part of the FWB/CoARA project, in the production of [a joint repository of practices](#) of the five institutions of the FWB, and proposed a list of best practices, areas for improvement, and suggested layouts for both research project assessment and research career evaluation (promotion and recruitment).
- Implemented guidelines for handling conflicts of interest, prior to any evaluation of its calls, and in the context of recruitment commissions.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Based on the results of the FWB/CoARA project, together with the partner universities from the FWB:
 - o Identify and analyse new indicators, tools and procedures for evaluating research.
 - o Propose indicators, tools or procedures for evaluating research that take into account all contributions.
 - o Establish avenues of appropriation within FWB institutions.
- **High priority** – Define a list of indicators, tools and procedures for evaluating FSR projects submitted to the Research Council.
- Dedicates the time of the Research Council to engage in ongoing reflection on its research funding tools and evaluation processes (e.g., annual meetings).

- The Research Council will share existing documentation or, if necessary, draw up a document setting out guidelines and recommendations for high-quality peer-reviewed publications and for avoiding publications in predatory journals.

Commitment 7: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.

UNamur already:

- Contributed to the development of an Open, Transparent, Merit-based Recruitment (OTM-R) guide ([e-book](#)), which promotes good recruitment procedures and practices.
- Initiated actions to improve transparency in recruitment practices:
 - o Through the creation of [a single portal](#) for all academic vacancies. Positions are advertised in a harmonised format on the UNamur portal and relayed via Euraxess. The job vacancy may also be published on other websites deemed appropriate.
 - o Through the transparency of the evaluation criteria
- Promotes the international recruitment of researchers (e.g., using the [Euraxess Jobs platform](#)).
- Is fully committed to promoting equality through the gender and non-discrimination policy of the University of Namur and the Isala Nova project
- Provides on-demand oral feedback:
 - o When evaluating research proposals:
 - Via a face-to-face meeting with the President of the Research Council for researchers who have submitted a research proposal.
 - o When evaluating research careers:
 - Via a face-to-face meeting with the President of the committee after a recruitment campaign. This is an assessment carried out as part of the recruitment process.
- Implemented a rebuttal phase in the evaluation procedure of the ARC, the institution's most important funding tool.
- Created a [poster](#), as part of the FWB/CoARA project, to inform the institution's scientific community that work is underway on reforming research evaluation.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Clarify its evaluation procedures for research projects (FSR)
- Promote communication on CoARA's commitments and on all institutional evaluation procedures within the university community.

Commitment 8: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.

UNamur already:

- Has been part of the FWB/CoARA project on the reform of research evaluation, developing an inter-university platform of good practices for research evaluation ([PINDARE](#)) in line with CoARA. This project involved the five universities of the FWB: ULB, ULiège, UMONS, UCLouvain and UNamur.

- Contributed to the development of an OTM-R guide ([e-book](#)) on good recruitment procedures and practices, as part of an inter-university project.
- Attends the CoARA General Assembly and thematic webinars to stay up to date with the latest trends.

UNamur will:

- Continue collaborating with its partner universities in the FWB through the inter-university FWB/CoARA project.
- Promote communication on CoARA's commitments within the university community.
- Continue to attend the CoARA General Assembly and some thematic webinars on the topic, in order to stay up to date with current trends.

Commitment 9: Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.

UNamur already:

- Informed its internal governance bodies about its engagement in signing the CoARA agreement and its participation in the FWB/CoARA project.
- Create a dedicated webpage on the University website explaining the CoARA coalition and the university's commitment to meeting its obligations.
- Make the FWB/CoARA project report freely available on the UNamur institutional repository.
- Communicate progress regarding CoARA in the PINDARE platform.

UNamur will:

- Report the progress made on this action plan annually to its internal governance bodies, through the Research Council's annual report.

Commitment 10: Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

UNamur already:

- Made a benchmark on qualitative evaluation criteria for research projects and academic career evaluation through the FWB/CoARA project.

UNamur will:

- **High priority** – Publish its action plan and progress made on its institutional website.
- **High priority** – Publish its action plan and progress made on the CoARA website.
- Take greater account of the literature devoted to research on research (for example, by inviting an expert to speak on this subject).

CoARA